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Abstract

This experiment investigated the effects of variable exposure durations and distinct cognitive tasks on visual performance. Exposure duration was manipulated across six intervals (50 ms, 75 ms, 100 ms, 125 ms, 150 ms, and 175 ms), while the cognitive task was varied across two conditions: a localization task and an identification task. Six male graduate psychology students aged between 24 and 26 years participated in the study. Stimuli consisting of 62 alphanumeric characters were generated using custom software and displayed on a monitor to calculate correct behavioral responses. The gathered data were analyzed via a two-way repeated measures ANOVA. The results demonstrated that the main effects of both exposure durations and task types on visual performance were statistically significant. Pair-wise comparisons confirmed that visual performance generally increased alongside longer exposure intervals, and performance scores were consistently higher during spatial localization tasks than during feature identification tasks.

Keywords: Visual Performance; Exposure Duration; Localization Task; Identification Task

VISUAL PERFORMANCE AS A FUNCTION OF EXPOSURE DURATIONS AND TASKS

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ABSTRACT

The present experiment investigated the effects of exposure durations and tasks on visual performance by manipulating exposure duration in six ways (50 ms, 75 ms, 100 ms, 125 ms, 150 ms, and 175 ms) and task in two ways (localization task and identification task). Six male graduate students of psychology aged between 24 and 26 years participated in the experiment. The program for generating stimuli was written with the help of a software named Microsoft Visual Studio 2005 which used the language C# (C-sharp). The stimuli composed of 62 alpha-numeric characters were presented on a 17 inch CRT Lenovo Monitor for computing the correct responses in visual performance. The obtained data were analyzed by two-way repeated measures ANOVA with a view to investigating the effects of exposure durations and tasks on visual performance. The ANOVA results showed that the main effects of exposure durations and tasks on visual performance were found to be significant. Post-hoc pair-wise comparisons (Ryan's method, $p < .05$) showed that visual performance varied significantly between all possible pairs of exposure durations except four pairs.

INTRODUCTION

Visual performance is accomplished by localizing and identifying an object in space because identity and location are two indispensable principles for measuring it. Therefore, visual performance is intervened and influenced by two essential processes which are as follows: (i) Object identification, and (ii) Object localization. Object identification means what the object is. It is concerned with assigning a (verbal) label or identity to an object. That is, it is the act of designating or identifying something. It is also the process of recognizing something or someone by remembering. Experimental psychologists identify objects by measuring the elapsed time from the onset of the stimulus to its recognition by the observers. On the other hand, Object localization means where the object is. It is concerned with determining its position in space. That is, localization refers to the processing of visual spatial information from the retinal input to the motor or perceptual output (e.g., Eggert, Salier, Ditterich & Straube, 2002).

There are three models which are used in describing the identification and localization of object. Among them, the three models are more important which are as follows: (a) a feature model (b) localization model, and (c) unconditioned model. First, the feature model is the model which states that localization processes are conditioned on identification processes. If feature localization processes are conditioned on feature identification processes as assumed by FIT, it is expected that the feature model provides the best fit to the data. Furthermore, at a performance level, identification performance may never be worse than localization performance. This model is basically a formalization of the original FIT (Treisman & Gelade, 1980). Second, localization model assumes that identification processes to be conditioned on localization processes. If feature identification processes are conditioned on feature localization processes as presumed by the theory of Sagi and Julesz (1985a), it is expected that the localization model provides the best fit to the data. Furthermore, localization performance may never be worse than identification performance. This model is the formal equivalent to the theory

of Sagi and Julesz (1985a, b). Third, the unconditional model assumes that localization and identification processes are not conditioned on each other. If feature localization processes and feature identification processes are not conditioned on each other, it is expected that the unconditional model provides the best fit to the data. Moreover, at a performance level, localization performance may be equal, worse, or better than identification performance dependent on the individual probabilities that the localization and identification processes are finished.

In the first seventy years of this century, visual research was primarily focused on processes of identification and form perception. Gestalt psychologists (e.g., Koffka, 1935) studied patterns of stimuli and described fundamental organizing principles. Researchers were interested in visual masking (e.g., Alpern, 1953) and studied how the identification of a target was impaired by a following or preceding masking stimulus. Neuropsychologists (e.g., Hubel & Wiesel, 1959) tried to determine feature specific cortical cells involved in pattern identification. It was not until the late sixties that an explicit distinction was proposed between two anatomically different neural systems processing either identity or location information (Held, 1968; Ingle, 1967; Schneider, 1967; Trevarthen, 1968). It has been observed that this early lack of concern with the role of spatial information in perceptual motor behavior may be related to a passive stimulus-response model of perception, which was then in vogue (Butter et al., 1982). In such a view, the perceiver is a passive recipient of environmental stimuli and not concerned with processes of orientation and localization which guide the active search for new information.

Other researchers (Dick & Dick (1969) were one of the first) who explicitly tried to assess separately the rate at which identity and location information is processed. Tachistoscopically, they presented one single letter in one of the four corners of an imaginary square centered upon the fixation point. Subjects were asked to report either the identity or spatial location of this letter. Their results showed that subjects were more accurate in localizing the letter than in identifying it. On the basis of this finding, Dick and Dick (1969) suggested that perception should be viewed as a hierarchical process where location information is processed before identity information. In a similar study, Smyth and Finkel (1974) presented very brief four geometric forms positioned in all but the middle square of an imaginary 3x3 grid, thereby providing eight possible stimulus locations. One group of subjects was asked to report the identity of the items, whereas another group was asked to report the spatial location of items. They (1974) found that subjects recalled more spatial information than identity information. They concluded that spatial information is processed more quickly than identity information, and that different mechanisms underlie spatial and object vision.

Research on visual search suggests that human vision operates in two sequentially arranged stages in which the operation of the second attentive stage is conditioned on the output of the first pre-attentive stage (e.g., Sagi & Julesz, 1985a; Treisman & Gelade, 1980; Wolfe, Cave & Franzel, 1989). Generally, the first stage is assumed to operate in parallel over the visual field. That is, visual information presented across the visual field is believed to be processed at the same time. The second stage, whose operation is conditioned on the output of the first one, presumably operates in a serial manner. Initially, it was suggested that the pre-attentive stage performs a feature analysis whereas the attentive stage is involved with localization and feature binding. According to the original feature integration theory (FIT), visual information is first analyzed into separate features (e.g., red or vertical) which are represented in distinct feature maps (Treisman & Gelade, 1980). Thus, in pre-attentive vision, primitive features are detected and identified (Folk & Egeth, 1989; Green, 1991; Treisman & Gelade, 1980;

Treisman & Gormican, 1988). Basically, pre-attentive processes signal what the identity is of a feature without signaling where it is. To localize a feature in the visual field the involvement of the second attention stage is required.

Another theoretical approach to visual search was provided by Sagi and Julesz (1985a, b) who suggested that the pre-attentive stage is capable of detection and localization whereas computations like discrimination and identification require the operation of the attentive stage. This notion is just opposite to the original notion of Treisman and Gelade (1980). Sagi and Julesz (1985 a, b) claimed that the pre-attentive stage is not able to identify features. Instead, the identification of even simple visual features is assumed to require the allocation of attention resources. The pre-attentive stage is capable to detect feature gradients if the display density is high enough. That is, feature differences or discontinuities can be computed in parallel if the distance between adjacent elements is relatively small. Apart from the detection of discontinuities, pre-attentive vision is also able to localize these discontinuities. Thus, according to this view, the pre-attentive system can signal where without knowing what the target is, except that it is different, whereas Treisman and Gelade (1980) assumed that localization processes were to be conditioned on feature identification processes. Sagi and Julesz (1985a) presume that identification processes to be conditioned on localization processes (Nothdurft, 1992; Sagi & Julesz, 1985b).

More recently, a theoretical point of view has been proposed (Cave & Wolfe, 1990; Treisman & Sato, 1990; Wolfe, 1994; Wolfe, Cave, & Franzel, 1989). Like in the original FIT, it is assumed that the pre-attentive stage in human vision is capable of detecting simple features across the visual field (Treisman & Gelade, 1980). In contrast to the original FIT, in this view, features cannot be preattentively identified. Instead, localization as well as feature identification processes is assumed to be performed by the attentive stage and conditioned on the output of the preattentive stage which only signals the presence of activity. Activity levels above some threshold indicate that some feature is present somewhere in the visual field. The identity and location of feature can be reported only if attention is allocated (Cave & Wolfe, 1990; Treisman & Sato, 1990; Wolfe, 1994; Wolfe, Cave & Franzel, 1989). In other words, no conditional relationship is assumed between localization and identification processes.

Evidence for one or the other theory primarily derives from studies directly comparing localization with identification performance. For example, Treisman and Gelade (1980) reported two experiments in which they had participants indicate the identity and location of a target that was concurrently presented with multiple distracters during a brief presentation time. One major finding was that feature identification was well above chance, even when major location errors were made. Furthermore, location responses were generally at chance when the target was wrongly indentured. Their conclusion was that the identification of features can be performed retentively but that the localization of elements requires the utilization of focused attention. Atkinson and Braddick (1989) came to different conclusion and showed that when in a localization task only "coarse" localization was required, performance was superior to that in an identification task. When in the localization task "fine" localization was required, localization and identification accuracies were equal. They concluded that processes related to "coarse" localization are preattentive and that processes of feature identification and "fine" localization are attentive. Saarinen (1996a) also manipulated a localization task and reported that it is possible to obtain data suggesting that localization processes precede identification processes, localization processes follow identification processes, or in which there seems to be no priority of one over the other. Finally, Green (1992) had participants

perform in a detection, localization, and identification task. His basic finding was that observers detected, localized, and identified targets with similar accuracies (Green, 1991, 1992). Saarinen (1996a) conducted experiments to measure reaction time and found that reaction time in the localization task was found to be longer than in the identification task. Another theory suggested that localization processes are conditioned on identification processes, the results of other studies seem to provide evidence for unconditional processing or for the idea that identification processes are conditioned on localization processes. A major reason for this disagreement might be related to the fact that in previous studies differences between localization performance and identification performance were directly interpreted in terms of which process precedes the other one. In other words, the relationship between localization processes and identification processes was directly inferred from divergences in performance. This is, however, not appropriate. Performance superiority in one task over the other does not justify the conclusion that processing related to the second task is conditional on processing related to the first one. Instead, it might as well be the case that both processes are not conditioned on each other (e.g., when they occur in parallel) but that the former is just faster than the latter resulting in better performance. In addition, neither does the absence of any difference in performance imply that both processes are unconditioned.

Donk and Meinecke (2001) reported that identification processes are conditioned on localization processes. In their study, observers are not able to indicate the identity of a simple feature unless they are able to determine at least coarsely where that feature is. These results unequivocally show a superior fit of the localization model over the feature model and the unconditioned model. Thus their results are not in accordance with any account assuming that identification precedes localization processes. The above review clearly showed that virtually localization without identification or vice versa could not take place.

Jos J. Adam and Marion Ketelaars, Herman Kingma, Theo Hock (1992) conducted an experiment to trace the processing time required to locate a single target stimulus. Employing a backward masking paradigm they established that the stimulus duration-localization performance function was characterized by two salient components: An early component reflecting an initial steep rise in localization performance, and a late component reflecting a gradual rise in localization performance. They interpreted these two components as reflecting the sequential operation of the attentional system and the eye movement system. These two systems can be seen as being complementary. The attentional system acts as an early warning system conveying location information quickly but coarsely; the eye movement system, on the other hand, acts slower but is capable of providing a finer degree of spatial resolution. This kind of two-process localization model has been anticipated by Atkinson and Braddick (1989) who explicitly contemplated the possibility that different processes may underlie localization performance at different levels of precision. They interpreted the steep rise in localization performance during the first 50 ms of exposure duration as being caused by a shift of attention to the target area. This interpretation is in concordance with work by Yantis and Jonides (1984) who showed that sudden onsets in the visual field command shifts of attention. Moreover, the outcome of another experiment that subjects (nearly) always executed an eye movement, suggests a close relationship between processes underlying covert shifts of attention and overt movements of the eyes. The fact that subjects (nearly) always executed an eye movement toward the presumed target location points to the interesting possibility that visual (i.e., oculomotor) localization performance and manual localization performance might be functionally related. According to the final gaze hypothesis, subjects

faced with a manual pointing or aiming task first execute an eye movement toward the target and subsequently try to generate a manual response whose end-position matches the gaze of the eyes. In other words, according to the final gaze hypothesis, the functional role of eye movements in aiming behavior is to provide the motor system with a spatial reference point defined in terms of the final gaze of the eyes.

Several authors have suggested that localization performance may depend on the nature of the localization response (e.g., Abrams & Landgraf, 1990; Bridgeman al., 1979; Levy-Schoen & Blanc-Garin, 1974; Paillard, 1987). They studied the relationship between stimulus identification and stimulus localization processes. For instance, instead of using the "*" character as the target stimulus alpha-numeric characters could be used. Visual perception performance then could be studied in three conditions: (1) identification only (subjects only have to report the identity of the target stimulus) (2) localization only (subjects only have to report the location of the target stimulus); and (3) identification and localization (subjects have to report both the identity and the location of the target stimulus). Comparing performance in Condition 1 and 2 as a function of stimulus duration would determine the relative processing rates of identity and location information. Comparing localization and identification performance in the dual-task condition (Condition3) with the respective performances in the single-task conditions (Conditions 1 and 2) would shed light on the issue whether localization and identity information are coded independently.

From the above discussion, it can be said that visual performance depends on several factors but especially exposure durations and tasks (localization and identification) that's why the purpose of the present experiment was to determine the effects of exposure durations and tasks on visual performance by varying the exposure duration in six ways and task in two ways

Hypothesis

1. To test whether visual performance would be varied by manipulating exposure durations (50 ms, 75 ms, 100 ms, 125 ms, 150 ms and 175 ms), and
2. To test whether visual performance would be varied by manipulating tasks (Localization task and identification task)

Variables

Dependent variable Visual performance

Independent variables

1. Exposure Durations (50 ms, 75 ms, 100 ms, 125 ms, 150 ms and 175 ms)
2. Tasks (Localization and identification tasks)

METHODS

Participants

Six graduate psychology students (6 male students) of Dhaka University participated in the present experiment as observers. The participant's ages ranged from 24 to 26 years with a mean age of 25 years who had normal or corrected-to-normal vision and had no previous experience with the localization and identification task. Each participant was strongly right-handed and also expert at pressing the right or left button of a mouse in a computer.

Apparatus and stimuli

Stimuli were exposed to view on a 17 inch CRT Lenovo Monitor (Model: 6307-BTE, Brand: IBM, Made in China, Voltage: 100-240~) with a pixel resolution of 1024×768 and a refresh rate of 100 Hz. The program for generating stimuli

was written with the help of Microsoft Visual Studio-2005 (Development Tool) and the language of that software was C# (C-sharp).

A stimuli display containing 62 alpha-numeric characters were composed of three horizontal lines. Of all stimuli, 60 characters were identical (e.g., S), and two were deviant characters which only arranged in the middle horizontal line. Among two deviant characters, one was dollar sign (\$) which was the target, and another was digit, named eight (8). The dollar sign (\$) contained the number eight (8) to either left or right of the dollar sign. There was a fixation point in the middle line which was the plus sign (+). Stimuli were black-colored and the background was white-colored where those stimuli were presented.

Stimuli were always presented in a region that subtended 22.93cm × 3.7 cm which was $31.99^{\circ} \times 5.30^{\circ}$ of visual angle at an observation distance of 40 cm. In 50% of the trials, the target contained the digit (8) to the left and in 50% of the trials it contained that digit to the right and both stimuli. Furthermore, the target was occurred only on the horizontal midline at a distance of 1.06, 2.12, 3.17, 4.33, 5.29, 6.35, 7.41, 8.46, 9.53 and 10.58 cm from the central fixation point which equal to 1.52° , 3.04° , 4.54° , 6.20° , 7.57° , 9.08° , 10.58° , 12.03° , 13.57° and 15.07° of visual angle. In the 62alpha-numeric characters condition, column distance and row distance was 1.06 cm (1.51° of visual angle).

The presented stimuli to the participants are given in the following figure:

Figure 1. Schematic representations of the stimuli where the target is dollar sign (\$), fixation point is plus sign (+). The digit (8) was presented to the left or right of the dollar sign.

Design

A two-factor repeated measurement design was used because the same participants were treated under two factors such as exposure duration and task where the former was varied in six ways (50 ms, 75 ms, 100 ms, 125 ms, 150 ms and 175 ms) and the latter was varied in two ways (localization task and identification task). The dependent variable was visual performance.

Procedure

The participants were requested to come to the Laboratory-3 (Sometimes, it is named as Dark Room) at the Department of Psychology in University of Dhaka. Then Participants sat in a comfortable chair and positioned in front of the computer monitor at a viewing distance of 40 cm. They viewed binocularly in dimly lit room.

Each Participant was instructed to accomplish two sequential tasks. In the localization task, each had to indicate whether the target (\$) occurred to the left or right of central fixation (+). In the identification task, each had to indicate whether the target (\$) appeared to left or right of the digit (8). Each combination of target location and target identity occurred equally often. Responses were made by means of pressing two mouse keys (left or right) That is, in the localization task, when the target stimulus occurred to left or

right of the central fixation point, participants had to keep the cursor to the left or right of the fixation point respectively and pressed the left or right mouse key respectively also. Again in the identification task, when the target stimulus appeared to the left or right of the digit (8), they had to keep the mouse cursor to the left or right of the fixation point and pressed the left or right mouse key respectively.

Each participant performed 1 session of 20 trials at each of the six stimulus durations and two tasks. That is, for six exposure durations and two tasks 120 trials were completed by each participant. In order to remove the order effects of exposure durations and tasks on visual performance, the exposure durations and tasks were administered in counter balanced way.

At the beginning of each trial, the central fixation sign and the quadrilateral box appeared together. Each trial started with the presentation of a ready signal (saying "ready?") immediately followed by the presentation of a central fixation point.

Stimuli were presented to each participant under six exposure durations (50 ms, 75 ms, 100 ms, 125 ms, 150 ms and 175 ms). After presentation of the stimuli, the participants were asked to accomplish two sequential responses (i.e., participants were instructed to give two responses at every trial which have mentioned before). After performing two responses, the stimuli were disappeared but the fixation sign was always present on the screen of the computer's monitor. After completion of each trial, the spacebar was pressed by the experimenter with a view to presenting the stimuli for the respective trial. In each exposure duration, the participants were given 20 trials to complete. That is, each participant had to complete 120 trials for six exposure durations.

Before starting of the next 20 trials for the respective exposure duration, each participant was free to take rest for 5 minutes only. If they did not perceive the location or the identity of the target, they were instructed to guess.

Before starting of the experiment, each inexperienced participant received 20 practice trials at each of the six exposure durations.

Basic data

All participants completed 20 trials under each exposure duration and task. The correct responses of visual performance were calculated for all participants under the six exposure durations and two tasks. The means of the visual performance were further calculated.

Data analysis

Data were analyzed by two-way repeated measures ANOVA with a view to investigating the effects of exposure durations and tasks on visual performance. Post-hoc tests (Ryan's method) for pair-wise comparisons of visual performance were carried out to determine which pair of exposure durations on visual performance was significantly different from each other.

RESULTS

The results obtained by two-way repeated measures ANOVA revealed that the main effects of exposure durations and tasks on visual performance were found to be significant and the interaction between exposure durations and tasks was not significant. The obtained results are given in the following tables:

Table 1: Mean visual performance as a function of exposure durations and tasks

Exposure durations	Tasks	
	Localization	Identification
50 ms	14.50 (87)	11.00 (71)
75 ms	17.00 (102)	12.50 (75)
100 ms	17.33 (104)	13.33 (80)
125 ms	18.33 (111)	14.33 (86)
150 ms	18.50 (113)	14.50 (87)
175 ms	19.17 (115)	15.67 (94)

Note. Number in parentheses indicate correct responses of visual performance

As shown in the Table 1, visual performance varied among six exposure durations. That is, visual performance increased with the increase in exposure durations. Again visual performance in localization task was better than the identification task.

Table 2: Analysis of variance of visual performance as a function of exposure durations and tasks

SV	SS	df	MS	F
Participants (A)	22.61	5	4.52	
Exposure durations (B)	421.78	5	84.36	24.13**
Tasks (C)	29.39	1	29.39	12.13*
A × B	87.39	25	3.50	
B × C	7.61	5	1.52	0.85
C × A	12.11	5	2.42	
A × B × C	44.89	25	1.80	

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .001$

As shown in the Table 2, the main effects of exposure durations and tasks on visual performance were found to be significant ($F_{5, 25} = 24.13$, $p < .001$; $F_{5, 25} = 12.13$, $p < .05$ respectively). But the interaction between exposure durations and tasks was not found to be significant.

Furthermore, visual performance was found to be different at least one of possible pairs of six exposure durations. However, we cannot determine which pair is significant? To answer this question, we further carried out post-hoc pair-wise comparisons of the exposure durations on visual performance. The post-hoc pair-wise comparisons (Ryan's method, $p < .05$) showed that the visual performance between the exposure durations of 100 ms and 125 ms, 100 ms and 150 ms, 75 ms and 125 ms, 100 ms and 175 ms, 75 ms and 150 ms, 50 ms and 125 ms, 75 ms and 175 ms, 100 ms and 50 ms, 175 ms and 125 ms, 75 ms and 50 ms, 150 ms and 125 ms were found to be significant. But for the pairs of 50 ms and 150 ms, 50 ms and 150 ms, 100 ms and 75 ms, 175 ms and 150 ms, the visual performance were not found to be significant.

Graphically the visual performance of exposure durations and tasks are presented in following way:

As shown in graph, the visual performance was differentiated among exposure durations. That is visual performance improved with the increase in exposure durations. On the other hand, visual performance in localization task was found to be greater than that of identification task.

DISCUSSION

The present experiment investigated to examine the effects of exposure durations and tasks on visual performance. It was hypothesized to test whether visual performance would be varied by manipulating exposure durations and to test whether visual performance would be varied by manipulating tasks.

The findings of the present experiment are as follows: (a) visual performance is significantly different from one exposure duration to another and post hoc pair wise comparisons have showed that visual performance is increased with the increase in exposure durations (b) the visual performance between two tasks is significantly different from each other, and (c) the interaction effect between exposure durations and tasks is not significant.

This first finding is consistent with the two process model of visual spatial localization of systematic studies by Adam et al. (1993). This finding is also congruent with the previous study of Jos J. Adam and Marion Ketelaars, Herman Kingma, Theo Hock (1992). However, one question has derived as to why localization performance was increased with the increase in exposure durations. This finding can be explained by the following way: first, it may be explained by two components: (a) the first component explores the initial steep rise in performance during the first 50 ms of stimulus duration followed by a plateau for the next 50 ms. This component can be influenced by attentional system (b) The second component represents the gradual rise in performance as a function of increasing stimulus durations from 100 ms onward, finishing with maximal performance at about 300 ms. This component can be influenced by eye movement system. Second, it may be explained that visual performance improves because of disengaging attention from its current location, moving to a new location, and managing the new location. Some researchers suggest this explanation demonstrating that independent of eye movements, attention can move to designated locations in space and improve the processing of visual stimuli at those locations (e.g., Ericson, 1990; Posner & Peterson, 1990; Posner & Presti, 1987; Stein, 1989).

Third, when an observer intends to achieve a greater precise localization performance than is accomplished by a shift of attention it is necessary to execute eye movement (saccade) to bring the fovea, with its high spatial acuity, to the new target location, mean response latencies of saccades are on the order of 200 ms with a distribution that ranges from about 100 ms to 300 ms (Eriksen, 1990). A speculative possibility is that eye movements underlie the second gradual rise component of the stimulus-duration localization performance function. This function shows a gradual rise in performance starting at about 100 ms stimulus duration and reaches maximal and asymptotic performance at about 300 ms. On the other hand, identification performance improved with the increase in exposure durations. However, one question may be aroused why identification performance improves with the increase in exposure durations? There may have several reasons for answering this question which are described in the following way: First, when an object or stimulus is suddenly appeared to an observer, it is more difficult for one to detect and identify that object or stimulus because of his or her becoming more attentive toward that object or stimulus. When a stimulus appears for a brief period of exposure duration, to keep and maintain a prolonged attention towards a stimulus somewhat difficult. That is, identification performance is coarse or lower within short period of time. But when exposure duration is increased, attention toward an object is also increased and identification performance is also better. Second, it can be explained by covert attention. Covert attention is the act of mentally focusing on one of several possible sensory stimuli. Covert attention is thought to be a neural process that enhances the signal from a particular part of the sensory panorama. Third, it can be explained by two attention stages: first, it was suggested that the pre-attentive stage performs a feature analysis where as the attentive stage is involved with localization and feature binding. According to the original feature integration theory (FIT), visual information is first analyzed into separate features (e.g., red or vertical) which are represented in distinct feature maps (Treisman & Gelade, 1980). Thus, in preattentive vision, primitive features are detected and identified (Folk & Egeth, 1989; Green, 1991; Treisman & Gelade, 1980; Treisman & Gormican, 1988). Basically, preattentive processes signal what the identity is of a feature without signaling where it is. To localize a feature in the visual field the involvement of the second attention stage is required. Finally, for a brief period of time, the participants are not able to show greater performance in identifying object because the observers have to be more conscious while viewing an object for a short period of time. That is, it may be said that since exposure duration of stimuli increases gradually, the observers can be more attentive, can give more attentional effort towards stimuli and also identify, localize and analyze the features of stimuli. Hence visual performance is varied among different exposure durations and it also increases with the increases in exposure durations.

The second finding is consistent with the previous study of Dick and Dick (1969) where location information is processed before identity information. These findings are also congruent with the previous study Smyth and Finkel (1974) exploring that subjects recalled more spatial information than the identity information. These findings are also congruent with the localization model which assumes that identification processes to be conditioned on localization processes. That is, visual performance in localization task may never be worse than identification task. These findings are also consistent with the previous study of Treisman & Gelade (1980). This finding can be explained by the following way: it may be explained by a theoretical approach exploring that localization performance is also mediated by a shift of attention followed by a saccade. That is, it may be explained neurophysiologically or neuroanatomically. Some researchers (e.g., Breitmeyer, 1984; Breitmeyer & Ganz, 1976) have identified a model of visual

information processing based on the spatial-temporal response properties of two types visual cells, which are responsible for identification and localization. These cells are (1) Sustained cells, and (2) Transient cells. Sustained cells process high spatial frequency, figural information in a slow but sustained manner. But transient cells on the other hand respond and conduct faster, react to abrupt onsets and offsets and process low frequency, location information. Sustained cells are most heavily concentrated at and near the fovea while transient cells are most dominant in extrafoveal areas (Fukuda & Stone, 1974; Stone, 1978). These two cells can be explained in the following way: when an object or stimuli suddenly appears in the visual field, transient cells signal its presence and location. Thereby acting as an early warning system for switching what Breitmeyer calls the functional locus of attention from the fovea to the extrafoveal location to expedite and enhance visual information processing. In order to bring the anatomical locus of attention i.e. the fovea with its high resolution sustained cells, to the newly selected area, a saccade is produced, allowing foveal sustained cells to do the fine-grain analysis. This fine grain-analysis is both concerned with figural (identity) and as with fine spatial (location) aspects (Robinson & Goldberg, 1978). The fact that response latencies of sustained cells are 50-100 ms slower than those of transient cells (Dow, 1974) accords nicely with this conception and with the observed time course of the localizations functions. There are several reasons for obtaining more visual performance in localization task than the identification task which are described in the following way: First, these findings can be explained by a theory suggesting that identification processes are conditioned on localization processes in dual task at a time (i.e., localization and identification task). For this reason, visual performance in localization is better than the identification task. Second, these may be explained study of Donk and Meinecke (2001) reporting in their experiments that identification processes are conditioned on localization processes. This suggests that at least in their experiment identification processes are conditioned on localization processes. Apparently, observers are not able to indicate the identity of a simple feature without knowing (at least coarsely) where that feature is. This finding is in strong agreement with the ideas of Sagi and Julesz (1985a, b) that localization precedes identification. Third, these findings can also be explained by two types of saccades influencing the visual performance in localization and identification task of an object or a stimulus. Visually guided saccades are responsible for localization performance and on the other hand, memory guided saccades are responsible for identification performance. Localization performance can be higher due to visual saccade movement but memory guided saccade is somewhat difficult for performing better identification. That's why in dual task condition, visual performance in localization is better than the identification task. Fourth, these findings may be explained by covert and overt attention. Overt attention is the act of directing sense organs towards a stimulus source. On the other hand, covert attention is the act of mentally focusing on one of several possible sensory stimuli. Covert attention is thought to be a neural process that enhances the signal from a particular part of the sensory panorama. Covert attention is a mechanism for quickly scanning the field of view for interesting locations. Since overt attention is controlled by sense organs and more responsible for identity of objects but overt attention is responsible for location and controlled by an organism, visual in localization task is better than the identification. Fifth, it can be explained by exogenous and endogenous attention which can influence visual performance. Exogenous attention is responsible for visual performance in localization task and for localizing an object an individual is not needed to be conscious but endogenous attention is responsible for identification task and individual is needed to be conscious to identify an object. For this reason, visual performance in localization task is better than the identification task.

The third finding is that the interaction effect between exposure durations and tasks is not significant indicating the visual performance of localization task may be higher than the identification task regardless of which exposure durations (male or female) are taken to measure the visual performance.

In conclusion, visual performance differs among different exposure durations and it can be increased with the increase in exposure durations. Again visual performance varies under different tasks, that is, visual performance in localization task is better than that of identification task. Therefore, visual performance varies under different exposure durations and tasks.

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